

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE INCIDENCE OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES IN THE FERGANA REGION

Abdulkhafizov Ubaydullo Akromovich

e.mail: abdulhafizovubajdullo@gmail.com,

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1120-4831>

Yunusov Ahrorjon Gulomjon ugli

e.mail: axroryunusov0519@gmail.com,

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9578-9695>

Central Asian Medical University.

Fergana, Uzbekistan.

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an analysis of the incidence of cardiovascular diseases among the population of Fergana region. The study was conducted using a retrospective analytical method based on official statistical data from regional health institutions for 2019-2023. The results indicate a steady growth trend in cardiovascular diseases in Fergana region, justifying the need to strengthen early diagnosis and preventive measures among the population.

Relevance. Cardiovascular diseases are one of the main nosological groups that pose a serious threat to the health of the population and are characterized by high mortality, reduced working capacity and disability. Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death globally. Approximately 55-60% of total deaths in Uzbekistan are due to cardiovascular diseases. The prevalence of cardiovascular diseases in our country, including in the Fergana region, remains at a consistently high level.

The purpose of the study. Analysis of cardiovascular disease incidence rates among the population of Fergana region for 2019-2023 and identification of main trends.

Materials and methods. In our study, the annual statistical reports of health institutions of Fergana region were analyzed. Retrospective and comparative analysis methods were used. Incidence rates were calculated per 100,000 inhabitants.

Results. According to the data obtained, in 2019, the total incidence of cardiovascular diseases in the Fergana region was 3,420 cases, while by 2023 this figure had reached 3,980 cases, i.e. an increase of 16.4%.

In the nosological structure of cardiovascular diseases:

- arterial hypertension – 52,6 %,
- ischemic heart diseases – 28,4 %,
- acute disorders of cerebral blood circulation – made up 9.7%.

In the analysis by age group, the highest incidence rates were found among the population aged 45-59 (41.2%) and over 60 (36.8%). In the analysis by gender, the incidence rate among men was 1.3 times higher than among women.

Conclusion. The data obtained showed a steady increase in the incidence of cardiovascular diseases among the population living in Fergana region. Arterial hypertension occupies a leading position in the incidence of cardiovascular diseases and is the main risk factor for the development of subsequent complications. This situation requires early diagnosis, control of risk factors and strengthening preventive measures among the population.

Based on the above, it is necessary to strengthen measures aimed at primary prevention, regular screening of the population and the formation of a healthy lifestyle in Fergana region.

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